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The effect of teaching on basic motor skills in boys' and girls' six years old of Tehran zone 9 and comparison with available norm
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Abstract: The purpose of this research was the study effects of teaching on basic motor skills in 6 years old boys and girls and its comparison with present norm. Statistical sample included 560 individual and divided to separate four groups of boys and girls as educated and uneducated (140 peoples per group). Research method was semi-experimental or comparative casual and for data collecting has been used basic motor abilities test (BMAT) or Raynham Sinkler Instrument of data collecting was test of basic motion skills, produced by Raynham– Sinkler (1974) that is for assessment of motion reflection at gross and fine muscle control children 4 – 12 years old, reliability of test by re-test for total test was count %89. The scores gained of tests were changed standard T score and recorded and then based on sex and type of education was categorized and compared. In this research was used of descriptive statistical methods (average and standard deviation) and inference like t-test and two-way factor analyze to comparative groups ($p \leq 0/05$). Results showed significant main effect of type of education and sex in fine skills and gross skills ($p \leq 0/05$). In fine skills, girls and educated and in gross skills, boys and uneducated act better than else. In some of skills interaction between type of education and sex showed significant. Also results showed scores average of subjects in more often sub-tests weaker than norm.

Keywords: Basic Motor Skills, Preschool, Norm, Gross and Fine Skills

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